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RESEARCH ARTICLE

2 **Modeling processing inaccuracies in human binaural processing of** 3 **speech using interaural mistuning**

4 Simon Weihe^{1,3*}, Bernd T. Meyer^{2,3}, Jan Rannies^{1,3,4}, and Thomas Brand^{1,3}

5 ¹ Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Department für Medizinische Physik und Akustik, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany

6 ² Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, Communication Acoustics, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany

7 ³ Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all

8 ⁴ Fraunhofer Institute for Digital Media Technology, Branch of Hearing Speech and Audio Technology, 26129 Oldenburg,
9 Germany

10 **Abstract** – Human speech intelligibility in noise improves when target speech and interferers differ in in-
11 teraural level and time differences, a phenomenon predicted by the equalization-cancellation (EC) model.
12 To avoid overestimating binaural benefit, human processing inaccuracies are modeled stochastically using
13 Monte Carlo simulations by some models. However, this approach is computationally expensive and unsuit-
14 able for many practical applications. This study introduces a deterministic mistuning approach to model
15 these inaccuracies in a blind, real-time capable framework. Instead of stochastic sampling, interaural gains
16 and delays are offset by a fixed amount to represent average perceptual uncertainty. The mistuned EC
17 stage is combined with a blind back end that estimates speech intelligibility from phone recognition out-
18 put. The model is evaluated across diverse acoustic conditions, including near- and far-field speech, varying
19 noise directions, non-frontal targets, and interaurally phase-inverted speech in diotic noise. Results show
20 that the mistuned model achieves prediction accuracy comparable to intrusive reference models, without
21 requiring clean speech or noise signals. The approach enables accurate, efficient, and blind prediction of
22 speech reception thresholds, making it suitable for continuous monitoring or even real-time implementation
23 in hearing aids and adaptive audio playback systems.

24 **Keywords.** Speech intelligibility, Auditory model, Binaural processing, Reverberation

25 1. Introduction

26 Human speech recognition in complex and noisy listening environments represents one of the most remarkable
27 features of human auditory processing. Computational models of human speech recognition are widely employed
28 to predict listener performance for individuals with and without hearing impairment across a variety of acoustic
29 conditions (e.g., [1], [2],[3]). These model predictions play a crucial role in research, clinical diagnostics and technology
30 development, supporting the design of hearing aids, speech tests, auditory training paradigms, and communication
31 devices.

32 In certain applications – such as the development and evaluation of diagnostic speech recognition tests – the
33 target speech and interfering noise signals are typically known a priori and can be provided to the model as clean,
34 separate inputs. Models that rely on such auxiliary information are termed intrusive or non-blind. In contrast, other
35 applications require models to operate solely on the mixture of speech and noise, without access to the original clean
36 signals. These models, which function without prior knowledge of the individual source components, are referred to as
37 blind or non-intrusive.

38 Blind models offer significant advantages: They can, for instance, be applied to unknown speech signals. They
39 can also be used for predicting the perceptual benefits of non-linear signal processing strategies commonly employed
40 in hearing aids and other assistive devices. In such systems, non-linear processing can introduce distortions and
41 intermodulation products that are difficult to attribute unambiguously to either the target speech or the background
42 noise. This poses a challenge for intrusive models, which often depend on precise knowledge of clean input signals and
43 rely on metrics such as the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for their predictions. By operating directly on the mixed and
44 possibly distorted signal, blind models provide a more realistic and robust framework for evaluating the impact of
45 complex, non-linear processing in real-world listening scenarios.

46 A further step toward practical implementation in hearing instruments is the development of real-time capable
47 models [4], [5]. Such models, which must operate with minimal computational overhead, hold the potential to be
48 integrated directly into hearing aids for online control of adaptive signal processing strategies. To achieve real-time
49 feasibility, these models must be computationally efficient while preserving predictive accuracy.

50 One important aspect accurate prediction models must account for is binaural processing. Humans understand
51 speech in background noise more effectively when differences between target speech and background noise allow for
52 perceptual unmasking. When speech and noise differ in their interaural level differences (ILD) and/or interaural time
53 differences (ITD), better-ear listening (BEL) and binaural unmasking occur, enhancing speech intelligibility (SI) [6].

* Corresponding author: simon.weihe@uni-oldenburg.de

54 This phenomenon can be modeled using the equalization-and-cancellation (EC) framework [7], which assumes that
55 interaural differences are equalized across ears and that the resulting signals are subtracted to cancel the noise or
56 to enhance the speech. However, to avoid overestimation of binaural benefit – particularly in anechoic conditions
57 – human processing inaccuracies must be considered in the EC process. Vom Hövel [8] refined earlier assumptions
58 [7] by modeling these inaccuracies as random variables that stochastically jitter the representations of speech and
59 noise, thereby simulating the variability in human binaural perception. He further quantified the resulting degradation
60 in SNR due to imperfect equalization. A similar analytical approach was adopted by [1], who derived the binaural
61 benefit directly as an SNR improvement without generating intermediate signals, enabling efficient prediction of
62 spatial unmasking. Related work by other researchers (e.g., [3],[9]) has further advanced this line of modeling, offering
63 alternative formulations for predicting binaural benefit under varying spatial configurations.

64 An alternative, signal-based approach was proposed by [10], who introduced processing inaccuracies by drawing
65 equalization parameters (for ILD and ITD) from zero-mean, Gaussian-distributed random variables – consistent with
66 vom Hövel’s model. This procedure was repeated across multiple Monte Carlo simulations (MCSs). The speech re-
67 ception threshold (SRT) – defined as the SNR at which 50% of words are correctly repeated – was computed as
68 the average across simulation runs. Figure 1 illustrates the SNR improvement caused by EC processing for different
69 equalization parameters, that is, equalization of interaural gain and interaural delay, in a gammatone band-pass filter
70 of the model of [10] for an exemplary condition with frontal speech and lateral noise source. The blue dots show the
71 resulting SNRs for different MCS samples. This method generates single-channel output signals that can be further
72 processed by downstream model stages, offering greater flexibility in model architecture. However, the MCS approach
73 means that the entire model has to run multiple times, making it computationally inefficient.

74 Hauth et al. [11] revised the model of [10] to develop a blind EC stage that does not require prior knowledge of
75 the clean speech or noise signals, nor assumptions about their direction of arrival. Instead, the model relies on the
76 assumption that the modulation spectrum of the interfering noise differs from that of speech – a condition frequently
77 met in real-world environments. In a related approach, [12] proposed a blind EC model under the assumption that
78 speech originates from the frontal direction, implying no interaural differences between speech and noise. Rather than
79 performing actual equalization and cancellation, their model estimates the net effect of such a process, offering a
80 computationally efficient alternative for predicting binaural benefit in spatially diffuse noise.

81 Wan et al. [13] introduced a further computationally efficient method by applying sample-wise jittering of speech
82 and noise waveforms in time and level using zero-mean Gaussian noise. While this approach avoids the computational

Figure 1. Example for resulting SNR after the equalization and cancellation process according to the model of [10] for speech coming from 0° and lateral noise depending on the interaural gain and delay equalization. Note that in this case a cancellation without any equalization would lead to the lowest possible SNR (blue peak to the bottom), while an optimal equalization would lead to an unrealistically high SNR improvement (red peak to the top). The realistic SNR at the SRT measured with normally hearing subjects is lower. The blue dots represent resulting SNRs after inserting statistical binaural inaccuracies in a Monte Carlo Simulation while the green dot indicates one representative mistuning as proposed in this study. The red and blue grids represent the SNRs at the better or worse ear in terms of SNR without binaural processing.

83 burden of MCS, it may introduce artifacts that disrupt downstream processing stages – such as automatic speech
 84 recognition (ASR) systems – used for blind prediction of human performance.

85 To be deployable for continuous monitoring or even real-time applications – such as adaptive hearing aids – a model
 86 has to be both blind and computationally efficient. Monte Carlo simulations, while effective for capturing variability,
 87 are inherently slow and thus unsuitable for online use. In this study, we replace the stochastic MCS framework with a
 88 deterministic approach: We introduce a fixed, representative inaccuracy – termed mistuning – that captures the average
 89 effect of human processing inaccuracy. The output of this mistuned EC stage serves as a stable, fixed representation of
 90 the signal and its processing uncertainty, enabling fast predictions without sacrificing the essential realism of binaural
 91 unmasking. The green dot in Figure 1 represents this mistuned setting of the binaural equalization parameters for
 92 the given example. In this study we determine the optimal setting of this mistuning and evaluate how closely this
 93 mistuning can approximate the MCS approach.

94 This paper is organized as follows: In Section 2 we describe the different models used in this study, the mistuning,
 95 and the datasets used for evaluation. All models used in this study are separated in a front end (predicting the
 96 consequence of binaural processing) and a back end (predicting speech intelligibility). In Section 3, we describe the
 97 evaluation of the mistuning approach. This was done in several steps: Firstly, we combined the blind mistuned front end

98 with a non-blind back end to a hybrid model. We evaluated this hybrid model using data from [10] for near-field speech,
99 different noise azimuths, and different room acoustics and compared the hybrid model’s predictions to predictions of
100 a non-blind reference model that used the same back end [10]. As the mistuned model performed suboptimally, we
101 slightly modified the non-blind back end. The results indicated that binaural effects can be well predicted by the new
102 front end, encouraging us to combine the mistuned front end with a real-time capable blind back end resulting in a
103 completely blind model, which was the core intension of this work. This blind model was then further evaluated with
104 different datasets for far-field speech, non-frontal target speech, and interaurally phase-inverted speech. Finally, we
105 discuss the results and the advantages and limits of the proposed approach.

106 2. Methods

107 2.1. Reference models

108 All models used in this study consist of a front end predicting the consequence of binaural processing and a back
109 end predicting the resulting speech intelligibility based on the output of this front end. The novel model proposed in
110 this study builds on previous models by [1], [10], [11], and [14], which also served as reference models in the studies
111 that have been reanalyzed here. These reference models, which are briefly described in the following, have in common
112 that they are not fully blind.

113 2.1.1. EC/SII model using Monte Carlo simulations

114 In the EC/SII model [10], the right and left input signals are divided into frequency bands using a Gammatone
115 filterbank [15]. This is done separately for speech and noise. Individual hearing thresholds are taken into account
116 through the use of threshold-simulating noise (TSN). The TSN, added to the external noise, is uncorrelated between
117 the left and right channel, and its power in each frequency band is 4dB above the power of a sine tone at the
118 individual’s hearing threshold level at that ear and frequency [16], [17]. The binaural benefit is modeled via an EC
119 processing stage based on [8], following [7], where the interaural equalization parameters gain and delay are optimized to
120 maximize the SNR in each frequency band. Inaccuracies in human binaural processing are incorporated stochastically
121 as random variables with standard deviations according to [8] (see Figure 2 upper panels). The output of the EC
122 processing are speech and noise signals with binaurally enhanced SNR. These signals are analyzed using the Speech
123 Intelligibility Index (SII) [18]. For including the random variables simulating individual processing inaccuracies, Monte
124 Carlo simulations are used, involving multiple repetitions of the process and averaging across the resulting outcomes,

125 which make this model slow in computation. As this model requires target speech and interfering noise to be provided
 126 separately, it is referred to as non-blind.

127 2.1.2. Analytical BSIM (2010) model

128 The Binaural Speech Intelligibility Model, BSIM (2010) [1] builds upon the EC/SII framework, but analytically
 129 computes the SNR values in each frequency band after EC processing – including stochastic uncertainties – and directly
 130 feeds the estimated band-wise energy of speech and noise into the SII. This approach accelerates the computation
 131 because Monte Carlo simulations are no longer required, but at the cost of not generating a binaurally enhanced signal,
 132 which limits its compatibility with arbitrary signal-based SI back ends. This model is also non-blind as it requires
 133 speech and noise signals separately.

134 2.1.3. UD₁₀₀ extension of BSIM

135 A sole analysis of SNR values, as done by the SII, fails to capture the detrimental effects of reverberation of the
 136 target speech on SI. The UD₁₀₀ extension [14] extends BSIM by decomposing the room impulse responses (RIR)
 137 into a useful and a detrimental part. Only the useful part is considered as target speech and the detrimental part is
 138 considered as part of the interfering noise. This approach requires the knowledge of the RIR as additional input data.
 139 The time, t_e , in milliseconds (ms) at which the RIR is split is denoted by the subscript “100”. Prior to EC processing,
 140 the clean speech signal is convolved with the useful part of the RIR up to t_e . In contrast, the convolution with the
 141 late, detrimental part of the RIR (where samples up to t_e are set to 0) is added to the noise signal. As this model
 142 requires speech and noise separately and additionally even auxiliary information about the RIR, it is also non-blind.

143 2.2. Blind EC front end

144 Hauth et al. [11] proposed a model, which performs the equalization process within each bandpass-filter based on
 145 the mixed speech and noise signals, i.e., without access to the separate speech and noise signals. In this model, the
 146 interaural level difference as well as the interaural delay of the bandpass-filtered speech and noise mixture is equalized.
 147 To perform the cancelation step, two different cases are distinguished: (1) the mixed signal is dominated by noise (i.e.,
 148 the SNR is negative) and (2) the signal is dominated by speech (i.e., the SNR is positive). In the former case, subtracting
 149 the equalized left and right ear signals improves the SNR by cancellation of the noise (referred to as EC_{min}), and in
 150 the latter case, adding the equalized signals improves the SNR by positive interference of the speech (referred to as
 151 EC_{max}). Both, the EC_{min} signal and the EC_{max} signal, are calculated and the estimated better one is selected based

152 on the “speech-likeness” of the signal modulations. A higher ratio of modulation energy at low modulation frequencies
153 to that at high modulation frequencies is considered to be less affected by noise or reverberation. Therefore, the EC
154 strategy leading to a higher ratio is selected. This approach is inspired by the speech-to-reverberation modulation
155 energy ratio (SRMR) proposed by [19] and its revision by [20]. In this study, the lowest modulation band center
156 frequency was set to 4 Hz and the highest to 40 Hz, leading to a crossover modulation frequency of 12.6 Hz between
157 what is considered “high” or “low”. However, we use it independently within each frequency channel, whereas [20]
158 proposed an energy thresholding method to truncate extremely low or high energies across frequencies, modulation
159 frequencies, and frames.

160 Motivated by Rayleigh’s duplex theory [21], only the lower frequency bands undergo this blind EC processing. The
161 cut of frequency is set to 1500 Hz. For higher frequency bands only the better ear (BE) is selected, i.e., the ear with the
162 estimated better SNR. The selection of the BE is based on the same criterion as for the EC strategy. Human binaural
163 processing inaccuracies are modeled using Monte Carlo simulations as in the EC/SII model described above.

164 This binaural front end performs blindly, as it does not require any auxiliary information about the clean speech
165 or noise signal. This approach does not make any assumption about the direction of arrival of speech and noise. Hauth
166 et al. [11] evaluated this blind front end in a hybrid approach using the non-blind SII back end. For that purpose,
167 shadow filtering was used, where the equalization parameters and the processing strategy as well as the selection of
168 the BE was based on the mixed signals and then applied to speech and noise separately. Hence, this model is also
169 non-blind.

170 2.3. Consideration of individual audiograms

171 Individual audiograms of normal-hearing subjects showed no influence on predicted SRT in noise in the results of [10]
172 and [14]. Therefore, in this study, individual hearing audiograms were not used for generating the TSN in predictions
173 of SRTs in noise; instead, a flat audiogram of 0 dB HL across all frequencies was assumed for all participants. This
174 approach considerably reduces computational time, as each SRT needs to be predicted only once, rather than once per
175 subject. An exception is the prediction of dataset II, which includes SRTs in quiet, where absolute individual hearing
176 audiograms do influence the predicted SRTs, even for normal-hearing listeners [14]. Hence, individual audiograms were
177 used to create TSN for the model predictions for this dataset.

178 2.4. Consideration of binaural processing inaccuracies using mistuning

179 In order to replace the Monte Carlo method, deterministic processing errors were derived in a manner such that
 180 the remaining time or level difference after equalization between the left and right channels is equivalent to the mean
 181 absolute artificial difference introduced by the Monte Carlo method used in [10] and [11]. This Monte Carlo method
 182 introduces inaccuracies given by normally distributed random variables with standard deviations that depend on the
 183 ITD and on the ILD as described in [8] and [10].

184 2.4.1. Magnitude of mistuning replacing stochastic inaccuracy

185 To derive a fixed mistuning with an effect equivalent to the Monte Carlo method on average, we seek the expectation
 186 value of the absolute value of a normally distributed random variable with zero mean, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[|X|]$ for $X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$,
 187 which is $\sqrt{2}/\sqrt{\pi} \cdot \sigma \approx 0.7979 \cdot \sigma$. A detailed derivation can be found in the appendix (Section 6).

188 Vom Hövel [8] utilizes two independent random variables, one for the right ear and one for the left ear. The
 189 difference between these two variables is then computed during the cancellation process. By virtue of the symmetry
 190 of the zero-mean normal distribution, this difference is statistically equivalent to the sum of two independent and
 191 identically distributed random variables, denoted as $X + Y$.

192 The sum of two independent random variables, $Z = X + Y$, follows a normal distribution $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_Z^2)$. The
 193 variance of Z is given by $\sigma_Z^2 = \text{Var}(X+Y) = \text{Var}(X) + \text{Var}(Y)$. Since the individual variances are equal (for a given ITD
 194 or ILD), we have $\sigma_Z^2 = 2\sigma^2$, and thus $\sigma_Z = \sqrt{2} \cdot \sigma$. As a result, the expected value $\mathbb{E}[|X+Y|]$ is also scaled by a factor of
 195 $\sqrt{2}$. Multiplied with the above derived expectation value for a single channel, we obtain $\sqrt{2} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}}\sigma = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}}\sigma \approx 1.1284 \cdot \sigma$
 196 for the difference between the left and right channel. Since the error is equally distributed across channels, the inserted
 197 new deterministic mistuning (per channel) is

$$\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \sigma / 2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sigma \approx 0.5642 \cdot \sigma. \quad (1)$$

198 A detailed derivation of the implementation can be found in the Appendix (Section 6.1) in addition to an alternative
 199 approach to determining the necessary amount of the mistuning (Section 6.2).

200 2.4.2. Direction of mistuning

201 In contrast to a zero-mean random variable, the sign of the fixed mistuning is relevant. The mistuning could
 202 be implemented in different ways like toward the right ear, toward left ear, overcompensating the ITD and ILD, or

203 undercompensating them. Preliminary simulations showed the best results for overcompensating ITD and ILD. This
 204 could be due to the fact that speech coming from a 0° azimuth is canceled if no equalization is performed, indicated by
 205 the minimum of the SNR shown in Figure 1. Without artificial inaccuracies, optimal equalization parameters (ITD and
 206 ILD) would lead to an unrealistically high SNR, represented by the red, sharp, highest peak in the SNR landscape. A
 207 fixed deviation, introducing more delay and gain toward one side, causes different effects depending on the direction of
 208 arrival of the dominant noise source. This would cause an asymmetry and is therefore not employed. In the direction
 209 of “no equalization” (zero delay and zero gain), the SNR drops very steeply, as seen toward the blue, sharp, lowest
 210 valley. Therefore, undercompensation is highly sensitive to small variations with the risk of heavily overestimation
 211 the SRTs. Moving in the opposite direction, the resulting SNR lies in a much flatter region of the SNR landscape.
 212 Overcompensation of the ITD and ILD therefore appears to be the best out of the four alternative approaches. Informal
 213 analyses confirmed this assumption and is in line with the assumption that the desired speech is more likely to come
 214 from the front than accidentally from the direction corresponding to the overcompensation.

215 2.4.3. Dependency of mistuning on required equalization parameters

216 According to [8] the mistuning per frequency channel depends on the required delay (Δ) for compensating the ITD
 217 and required gain (α) for compensating the ILD of the input signals as

$$mis_\delta = \frac{s}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sigma_{\delta_0} \left(1 + \frac{|\Delta|}{\Delta_0} \right), \quad s = \begin{cases} +1 & \Delta > 0 \\ -1 & \Delta \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

$$mis_\epsilon = \frac{s}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sigma_{\epsilon_0} \left[1 + \left(\frac{|\alpha|}{\alpha_0} \right)^p \right], \quad s = \begin{cases} +1 & \alpha > 0 \\ -1 & \alpha \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

218 with the parameters $\sigma_{\delta_0} = 65 \mu\text{s}$, $\Delta_0 = 1.6 \text{ ms}$, $\sigma_{\epsilon_0} = 1.5 \text{ dB}$, $\alpha_0 = 13 \text{ dB}$, $p = 1.6$ derived by [8]. Figure 2 illustrates
 219 the stochastic inaccuracies, as utilized by [10], in the upper panels, and the proposed deterministic mistuning in the
 220 lower panels.

221 The final front end with these mistuning parameters is referred to as Mistuned Blind Equalization-Cancellation
 222 (MisBEC) front end in the following.

Figure 2. Modeling of binaural inaccuracies in the equalization stage. Upper row: Standard deviation per channel of stochastic inaccuracies in gain (left) and delay (right) of the original model [8], [10]. Lower row: Fixed mistuning between channels in gain (left) and delay (right).

233 2.5. Model back ends

234 To test the compatibility of the proposed MisBEC front end with different model back ends, two types of model
 235 back ends were tested. The first type of back ends was based on the (non-blind) SII, the second type on the (blind)
 236 mean temporal distance (MTD) measure. Each back end produces a single-value measure representing the estimated
 237 SI for a given set of input signals. In order to predict SRTs values, the model needs to be calibrated to the used
 238 speech material in a reference condition (RC). This was done separately for each dataset. In each case, an anechoic
 239 constellation was used, in which no binaural unmasking (BU) was possible: either speech and noise were collocated
 230 from the front (S_0N_0) or diotic. For these RCs, the model was run using speech and noise input mixed at an SNR
 231 corresponding to the empirically determined mean SRT of normal-hearing subjects in the respective RC. The resulting
 232 model output value was then used as reference value representing 50% SI. To predict SRTs in other spatial and acoustic
 233 conditions, the SNR was varied until the reference value was reached within small margins, which correspond to an
 234 uncertainty of about ± 0.5 dB in SNR. For the MTD back end, smoothed interpolation between predicted SNRs was
 235 applied to account for statistical uncertainty (see Section 2.5.2).

236 The evaluations consisted of predicting various SRT measurements from the literature as well as a newly measured
 237 data set as described below. All measurements and predictions were conducted using the speech and noise material
 238 from the German matrix sentence test (Oldenburg sentence test, [22],[23],[24]). For a review of the matrix sentence
 239 test concept, the reader is referred to [25]. Each sentence has the same syntax: name - verb - numeral - adjective

240 - object. For every position, there are ten different word alternatives, which can be randomly combined to produce
241 syntactically correct, but semantically unpredictable sentences. In practice, the test consists of ten fixed equivalent
242 test lists, each containing every word once. From these lists, only the first was used for this study, except for dataset
243 II, where all test lists were used. The stationary masking noise of the test is a multiple superposition of the speech to
244 ensure the same long-term spectrum.

245 2.5.1. Intrusive reference back ends based on the SII

246 In a first step, the modified front end was combined with the established SII [18], similar to [11]. This combined
247 model will be referred to as MisBEC-SII. Simplified, the SII evaluates SNRs in frequency bands with a dynamic range
248 from -15 to $+15$ dB, maps this logarithmic range to linear indices from 0 to 1, and builds a weighted sum to obtain
249 a single index.

250 Diverging from the ANSI standard, the frequency channels were adapted to the frequency division of the gammatone
251 filterbank of the front end, as described by [1]. This allowed the SII values to be directly derived from the band-wise
252 speech and noise power values after the binaural processing of the front end, without requiring signal reconstruction. An
253 ideal shadow filtering was used, where the blindly estimated equalization parameters were used to process the speech
254 and noise signals separately. For performance reasons, it was exploited that the SII increases almost monotonically with
255 increasing SNR and is almost linear around the reference SNR. Consequently, the SNR was varied using a gradient
256 method between iterations. This procedure was performed per sentence and the predicted SRT was derived as the
257 mean SRT across all sentences tested in this condition.

258 The straightforward combination of the proposed front end with the SII resulted in stronger deviations between
259 predictions and measurement than expected for some conditions (see below), although the SII had worked well with
260 the non-blind front end. To follow up on this observation, two modifications of the SII were tested. First, the lower
261 bound of the internal dynamic range was varied from -18 to -2 dB, as prior experience suggested that this parameter
262 – reflecting the SII’s internal SNR limitation – can critically influence prediction accuracy. Preliminary tests revealed
263 that a lower bound of -10 dB yielded the best predictions for the given speech material and spatial configurations
264 (see Section 2.5 and 2.6.1). Bounds set above -7 dB resulted in some sentences being assigned an SII index value of 0
265 (above -3 dB this was true for all sentences), indicating that no intelligibility could be assessed by the SII when the
266 parameter was set too high. The model employing this limited dynamic approach with lower bound set to -10 dB is
267 referred to as MisBEC-SIILD.

268 Second, the summation of the weighted indices per frequency band was performed not in the logarithmic (dB)
 269 domain, but rather in the linear domain as done in the spectral speech-to-disturbance ratio (SDR) in [26]. The model
 270 employing this linear summation approach is referred to as MisBEC-SII.LS. Both approaches essentially result in a
 271 model neglecting the frequency bands with the lowest SNRs.

272 2.5.2. Blind Mean Temporal Distance (MTD) back end

273 In order to develop a fully blind model, the MisBEC front end was combined with a back end, referred to as the
 274 MTD back end, based on phone probabilities obtained from a deep neural network (DNN), as described in [27]. The
 275 resulting model, referred to as MisBEC-M, is similar in principle to the “Binaural ASR-based Prediction of Speech
 276 Intelligibility” (BAPSI) approach introduced by [28] and relies on the same English-only training data. However, the
 277 key difference lies in the use of time-consuming MCSs to determine the psychometric functions in [28], whereas the
 278 present model employs the fixed mistuning in the binaural stage.

279 The backend is obtained by following the procedure outlined in [27]: We trained a regular ASR system with a hybrid
 280 architecture; this includes a DNN that serves as acoustic model (and which produces phone posterior probabilities)
 281 and a hidden Markov model (HMM) for word or sentence recognition. For modeling purposes, the HMM remains
 282 unused; instead, model predictions are obtained from the phone posteriors alone. The degradation of posteriors in the
 283 presence of noise or other detrimental acoustic factors results in less distinct phone probabilities per time step, which
 284 is quantified with the MTD [29]. The MTD measures the average distance of phone vectors (based on the symmetric
 285 Kullback-Leibler divergence) over time intervals from 350 to 800 ms in steps of 50 ms, as defined in [28]. This metric
 286 tends to be lower in acoustically challenging conditions. This approach has also been explored for predicting perceived
 287 listening effort and speech quality. However, in the following, we focus on studies that investigate speech intelligibility
 288 as target metric.

289 The derivation of predicted SRTs from MTD values employed the same RC as for the SII back ends. However, the
 290 simulation and search method for obtaining SRT was adapted to accommodate the properties of the MTD back end.
 291 Specifically, one list of ten sentences was analyzed at once because the analysis window of the back end spans 850 ms,
 292 which is equivalent to the length of half a sentence. Furthermore, because the increase of MTD values with SNR was
 293 not strictly monotonic, as illustrated in Figure 3 (see black squares at SNRs of 10 to 12 dB), the gradient method
 294 was discarded in favor of a mapping function between SNR and MTD. This mapping function was generated for each
 295 acoustic and spatial condition by simulating a range of SNRs and fitting a spline smoothing interpolation curve to
 296 the resulting data points (see Figure 3). The procedure was used to determine the reference MTD value for a given

Figure 3. The relationship between mean temporal distance (MTD) values and signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) is illustrated, with MTDs calculated for both a reference condition (represented by small black squares) and a test condition (represented by small grey dots). For each dataset, a smoothed spline interpolation curve is calculated, yielding a black line for the reference condition and a grey line for the test condition. The light grey arrows depict the process of using these curves to derive a predicted speech reception threshold (SRT). Specifically, a reference SNR obtained from SRT measurements is used to determine a reference MTD value (denoted by a big black square), which is then used to predict the SRT (represented by a big grey dot) in the test condition, thereby establishing a mapping between the reference and test conditions based on the MTD values.

297 mean measured SRT and, subsequently, to predict SRTs in other conditions using the inverse mapping function with
 298 the reference MTD value (see light grey arrows in Figure 3).

299 2.6. Datasets and reference studies

300 2.6.1. Dataset I: SRTs of near-field speech with different noise azimuths and room acoustics

301 Dataset I was taken from [10] and consists of SRT measurements of eight normally hearing subjects in three different
 302 acoustic environments (anechoic, office, and cafeteria). Virtual source positions in the horizontal plane were simulated
 303 by convolving the speech and noise signals with binaural head-related impulse responses (HRIRs). All HRIRs were
 304 measured with a KEMAR head and torso simulator. The HRIRs for the anechoic condition were taken from a clone
 305 [30] of the CIPIC HRTF database [31]. The other HRIRs were measured by [10]. Every configuration consisted of a
 306 frontal speech source and a noise source presented from one of eight different angles in the horizontal plane (azimuth).
 307 The distance of the sources to the virtual listener’s head center was 1.4 m. The subjects listened to the stimuli through
 308 circumaural closed audiometric headphones of type HDA 200 (Sennheiser, Wedemark, Germany), which were free-field
 309 equalized using FIR filters (according to ISO 389-8:2004, Annex C). The reference model for this dataset used in [10]

Table 1. Mean measured SRT values in the RCs which served as reference SNRs to determine the corresponding reference MTD values for each dataset.

Dataset	I	II	III	IV
Mean SRT	-8.0	-8.1	-7.3	-8.4
Ref. MTD	7.6	7.1	7.7	7.3

310 is the EC/SII model described in Section 2.1.1. This dataset was chosen because it represents conditions in which
 311 binaural benefit results from the combined effects of better-ear listening and binaural unmasking. It also illustrates the
 312 reduced binaural benefit in reverberation compared to anechoic conditions due to the effects of reverberation on the
 313 noise masker. The mean measured SRT of the normally hearing subjects in the RC (S_0N_0) was at an SNR of -8.0 dB
 314 in [10]. This resulted in a reference SII value of 0.165 and a reference MTD value of 7.6 (see Table 1).

315 2.6.2. Dataset II: SRTs of far-field speech with different noise azimuths in noise and in quiet

316 In dataset I the target speech was not strongly reverberated due to its proximity to the listener. In contrast,
 317 conditions of dataset II [14] systematically varied the distance between sources and listeners, also including far-field
 318 target speech and far-field noises characterized by very low direct-to-reverberant energy ratios (DRRs). This dataset
 319 hence also included the detrimental effects of reverberation on the target speech. Furthermore, SRT were measured
 320 both in noise and in quiet, allowing us to test the effect of the TSN. In [14], measured SRT were compared to different
 321 extensions of BSIM. The best performing model was UD₁₀₀ (described in Section 2.1.3) which is thus used as reference
 322 model in this study.

323 The HRIRs of the acoustic conditions were generated using room acoustic software CATT-Acoustics v8.0a (CATT,
 324 Gothenburg, Sweden) with a modeled KEMAR head and torso as receiver. In the conditions in noise, speech was
 325 always presented from the front at four distances: 0.5, 1.5, 3.5, and 13 m. Noise was presented from the same position
 326 (S_0N_0) or from an azimuth angle of 22.5° ($S_0N_{22.5}$) or 90° (S_0N_{90}) to the right. The distance between noise source
 327 and listener was always the same as the distance between the speech source and the listeners, except for the receiver
 328 furthest away (position 4), where the distance of the noise sources from the side was also set to 3.5 m due to limited
 329 size of the room. In the conditions in quiet, speech was presented from the front (S_0) or from 90° to the right (S_{90}),
 330 corresponding to the same source positions used in noisy conditions. A schematic sketch is provided in Fig. 1 in [14].

331 Eight normally hearing subjects (three female, five male) between 23 and 28 years with pure tone thresholds
 332 ≤ 15 dB HL at frequencies between 125 and 8000 Hz (except one with a threshold of 20 dB HL at 8 kHz participated in
 333 the study. Since [14] reported an influence of individual pure tone audiograms on predicted SRTs in quiet, dataset II
 334 was predicted with individual hearing thresholds in this study. Twenty sentences were used for each SRT, as it was

335 the case in the measurements with the subjects. For that purpose, two out of ten test lists with ten sentences each
 336 were chosen randomly to predict one SRT and kept constant for the range of different SNRs tested to find the SRT.
 337 A repeated random ordering of all test lists across position combinations and subjects (i.e., their respective pure-tone
 338 audiograms) ensured that the entire speech material was used evenly. The reference SRT and MTD value are given in
 339 Table 1.

340 2.6.3. Dataset III: SRT benefits for symmetrical directions of arrival of speech and noise

341 Dataset III [32] was included to test the model in conditions with non-frontal speech. Speech was presented from dif-
 342 ferent azimuth angles and the noise source was always placed symmetrically relative to the frontal direction ($S_{-\alpha}N_{+\alpha}$).
 343 Ten subjects with normal hearing (age 21 to 26 years) were seated in a chair with their head fixed, while loudspeakers
 344 were positioned on a semicircle with a radius of 1 m around the head in a sound insulated room with a relatively short
 345 reverberation time (0.35 s). To achieve small angles down to 0° , the height of the loudspeakers was slightly adjusted.
 346 The level of the noise was 60 dB SPL. For the predictions, speech and noise were recorded separately from different
 347 angles in steps of 5° using a KU 100 head simulator (Neumann, Berlin, Germany). The measured SRT data was
 348 analyzed with respect to spatial unmasking, i.e., SRT differences relative to the co-located reference condition. The
 349 reference SRT and MTD value are given in Table 1.

350 2.6.4. Dataset IV: binaural unmasking of phase-inverted speech in diotic noise

351 Datasets I-III comprised conditions with real or simulated sound sources placed around the listener. In such con-
 352 ditions, the benefits due to better-ear listening and binaural unmasking cannot be easily disentangled. To explicitly
 353 test the proposed model front end and its ability to predict binaural unmasking, dataset IV was measured in this
 354 study. The same speech material, masking noise, and procedure of the Oldenburg sentence test as used in the other
 355 datasets was used. Speech was presented either diotically (S_0) or phase-inverted on one side (S_π), while noise was
 356 always presented diotically (N_0). The noise level was always 65 dB SPL, while the speech level was varied adaptively
 357 to converge to SNRs corresponding to 20% and 80% correctly understood words, respectively. These values were used
 358 to fit psychometric functions, from which SRT values were derived. Thirteen normally hearing subjects participated
 359 in the experiments (pure-tone air conduction hearing thresholds of no more than 25 dB HL at audiometric frequencies
 360 from 125 Hz to 8 kHz in both ears). All stimuli were generated and controlled using Matlab (Natick, MA, USA), with
 361 the AFC-Matlab framework of [33], [34], [35] used to measure SRTs. The digital output was D/A converted via an
 362 RME Fireface UC (ASIO) sound card (RME, Chemnitz, Germany), amplified using a Tucker-Davis HB7 headphone

Figure 4. SRTs for the German matrix test OLSA in three acoustic environments with one noise source from different azimuth angles and speech from front 0° according to [10] FIG. 2. Note: SRTs at -180° are copied from 180° to emphasize the plots' symmetry. Filled circles: mean measurement \pm interindividual standard deviation (error bars and gray shaded area). Open symbols: model predictions; diamonds: with standard SII, left pointing triangles: with modified SII with reduced evaluated SNR-range to $-10 \dots +15$ dB, right pointing triangles: with modified SII with linear summation of frequency-band dependent SNRs. Virtual rooms were anechoic (left panel), an office (middle panel) and a cafeteria (right panel).

363 amplifier (Tucker-Davis Technologies, Alachua, FL, USA), and delivered to the subjects via HD 650 headphones
 364 (Sennheiser, Wedemark, Germany) in a sound-attenuated booth. The setup was calibrated for SPL using a Brüel and
 365 Kjær (B&K, Nærum, Denmark) 4153 artificial ear, a B&K 4134 1/2" microphone, a B&K 2669 preamplifier and a
 366 B&K 2610 measuring amplifier, with the right ear serving as the reference point for calibration, but the level of the
 367 two ears was always the same. The reference SRT and MTD value are given in Table 1.

368 3. Results and Discussion

369 3.1. Dataset I: SRTs of near-field speech with different noise azimuths and room acoustics

370 Dataset I was very well predicted by the original EC/SII model [10] and was therefore chosen to serve as the
 371 initial dataset to test the proposed front end. The model evaluation was conducted in two steps. First, the front end
 372 was combined with the standard SII. This resulted in discrepancies, based on which two back end modifications were
 373 introduced to the SII as described above. Second, the front end was combined with the blind MTD back end.

374 3.1.1. Evaluation with intrusive reference back end SII

375 Filled symbols in Figure 4 show the mean SRT data of [10] with interindividual standard deviations (error bars, gray
 376 shaded area) as a function of noise azimuth for speech presented from the front for three different acoustic environments

Figure 5. Same as Figure 4 but here predicted SRT of the fully blind MisBEC-M Model (open upward pointing triangles) are shown in comparison with the classic intrusive EC/SII model (open circles, replotted from [10] FIG. 2.).

377 (anechoic, office, and cafeteria). Open symbols show predictions of the half-blind models: MisBEC-SII (diamonds) with
 378 the standard SII as back end, MisBEC-SII_LD (left pointing triangles) with modified SII considering band-specific
 379 SNR ranges from -10 to 15 dB, and MisBEC-SII_LS (right pointing triangles) with modified SII considering the band-
 380 specific SNR in the linear domain. Predictions with the standard SII show raised SRTs and reduced binaural benefit
 381 in comparison to the subjects in the rooms with natural reverberation (office, cafeteria). Both suggested modifications
 382 show an improvement, while slightly overestimating the benefit in anechoic conditions. In Table 2 statistical measures
 383 of the prediction errors are given for the different MisBEC-SII versions.

384 3.1.2. Evaluation with blind MTD back end

385 Figure 5 shows the same data as Figure 4 together with predictions using the MisBEC-M model (upward pointing
 386 triangles). For comparison, the predictions of the original intrusive EC/SII model of [10] are replotted (open circles).
 387 The predictions of MisBEC-M are mostly within the measurements' standard deviation except for a noise azimuths
 388 of 180° in the anechoic condition, 125° in the office, and 45° in the cafeteria. There is no apparent trend for a general
 389 over- oder underestimation of SRTs.

390 The statistical measures of the predictions are given in Table 2 for comparison with the intrusive measures. Despite
 391 having less information, the new blind model MisBEC-M provides almost as accurate SRT predictions as the intrusive
 392 original EC/SII model regarding most of the prediction error measures. The greatest absolute deviation is even slightly
 393 smaller.

394 One way of considering interindividual variability in the context of model predictions is to use the data of individual
 395 subjects to predict the average SRTs. Table 2 compares the model predictions to the interindividual scattering observed
 396 in the measured data. To assess prediction accuracy relative to this variability, the right column shows the magnitude
 397 of the interindividual scattering for the model-derived statistical measures. For this, the SRT of each subject was
 398 treated as a prediction for the group average, and the resulting statistics were averaged across subjects to represent a
 399 “typical” subject.

400 Note that the bias cancels out due to this averaging and is consequently not listed in the table. The predictive
 401 power of a typical subject is very close to those of the MisBEC-M model, and also to those of the intrusive models,
 402 indicating that the uncertainty of the predictions is not larger than the interindividual differences.

Table 2. Performance metrics bias (mean error), mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE), maximum absolute error (MaxAE), and squared correlation coefficient (R^2) comparing model predictions to the data of [10]. The last column presents the average prediction power of a single normal hearing subject, calculated by treating each of the eight subjects’ measured SRTs as model prediction and reporting the mean across all subjects for each metric.

	EC/SII (non-blind)	MisBEC-SII (non-blind)			MisBEC-M (blind)	typ. subject (mean)
		Standard	LD	LS		
Bias / dB	−0.4	0.7	−0.7	−0.2	0.4	
MAE / dB	0.8	1.1	0.8	0.7	1.0	1.0
RMSE / dB	1.1	1.2	1.2	0.9	1.3	1.2
MaxAE / dB	3.5	2.2	3.3	2.4	3.0	2.4
R^2	0.94	0.92	0.95	0.94	0.91	0.93

403 3.2. Dataset II – SRTs of far-field speech with different noise azimuths in noise and in quiet

404 3.2.1. SRTs in noise

405 The left panel of Figure 6 shows mean SRTs ± 1 standard error across subjects for the different acoustic conditions
 406 of [14]. The middle and right panel show predicted SRTs of the MisBEC-M model and for comparison predictions of
 407 the UD₁₀₀ model and the original BSIM (gray) [14]. The reference condition with diotic representation of the standard
 408 speech and noise without reverberation is indicated by the diamonds. The symbols represent the noise azimuths (circles:
 409 0°, squares: 22.5°, triangles: 90°). SRTs are shown as a function of receiver positions from 1-4 with increasing distances
 410 between source and receiver causing decreasing DRRs. The measured data show decreasing SRTs with increasing
 411 noise azimuth (from 0° to 90°) indicating a binaural benefit, which decreases with increasing distance between source
 412 and receiver. The data further show a general increase in SRTs with increasing distance indicating the detrimental
 413 influence of the reverberation on the target speech.

Figure 6. Left panel: Experimentally measured SRTs data of dataset II for three noise azimuths (different symbols) at four distinct receiver positions with increasing distance between speech source and receiver. The diotic reference condition without reverberation is denoted by the diamond symbol. Error bars represent interindividual standard errors. Middle panel: Predictions of the MisBEC-M model. Right panel: predictions of the UD₁₀₀ model. For comparison, predictions of the original BSIM (gray lines) are replotted from [14] (Fig. 3) in the middle and right panel.

414 The original BSIM (gray) predicted the binaural benefit at receiver position 1 well, and also the decrease in
 415 binaural benefit with increasing distance. However, it failed to predict the generally increasing SRTs with increasing
 416 distance, revealing that it does not consider the detrimental effect of reverberation on the target speech. To overcome
 417 this shortcoming [14] introduced the distinction between useful and detrimental parts of the binaural room impulse
 418 response (BRIR) as described above, which produced very accurate predictions of the experimental data (right panel).

419 Predictions of MisBEC-M are shown in the middle panel. The model predicts all effects dominating this data set:
 420 increasing SRTs with decreasing noise azimuth, the interaction of binaural benefit and source-receiver distance, and
 421 generally increasing SRT with increasing receiver distance. This indicates that the front end is able to blindly predict
 422 the binaural benefit in reverberant conditions, and that the back end is able to blindly assess the detrimental effect of
 423 reverberation.

424 Figure 7 presents scatterplots of measured vs. predicted SRTs. Individual data are represented by open symbols,
 425 mean values across subjects are indicated by filled symbols. Different symbols denote the different conditions: circles
 426 for 0°, squares for 22.5°, triangles for 90° noise azimuth, and diamonds for the diotic reference condition without
 427 reverberation.

428 The approximately vertical scatter of the open symbols in the left and right panels indicates that the individual
 429 audiograms had a negligible influence on the simulation results in noise of BSIM and UD₁₀₀ models, i.e., that the
 430 small differences between hearing thresholds of the normally hearing subjects in this study caused nearly identical
 431 model predictions. In contrast, the slightly broader scatter in the middle panel in the predicted SRTs suggests that

Figure 7. The middle panel illustrates the correlation analysis of predicted and measured SRTs pooled over all noise azimuths (circles: 0° , squares: 22.5° , triangles: 90°) and source-receiver distances for the MisBEC-M model. The diotic reference condition is shown as diamonds. Individual SRTs values are represented by open symbols, while mean SRTs values are indicated by filled symbols. The distances along the x-axis between the least mean-square error fits with unity slopes (represented by the dashed lines) and the lines of perfect agreement (i.e., the bisecting lines) provide a visual representation of the prediction biases. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , is given for both individual data and mean data (in parentheses). For comparison, the corresponding scatterplots of the original BSIM (left panel) and UD₁₀₀ model (right panel) are replotted from [14] (Fig. 4).

432 the MisBEC-M model exhibits a greater variability in its predictions, which can be attributed to either a random
 433 component of the model or the fact that it analyzed two different random OLSA test lists per subject, whereas the
 434 other models considered an identical short noise sample representing the long-term spectrum of the target speech for
 435 each simulation. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , is nearly identical for MisBEC-M and UD₁₀₀ and notably higher
 436 than for BSIM, for both individual and mean (in parentheses) data. Furthermore, the bias of the predictions is smaller
 437 for MisBEC-M and UD₁₀₀ compared to the original BSIM, with the MisBEC-M model exhibiting the smallest bias,
 438 albeit only marginally.

439 3.2.2. SRTs in quiet

440 Figure 8 presents predicted and measured SRTs in quiet, displayed in the same manner as Figure 6. In this case,
 441 the different azimuth angles (circles: 0° , triangles: 90°) refer to the direction of the speech source. The diamond symbol
 442 represents the diotic condition without reverberation. However, it is essential to note that the reference for calibrating
 443 the models is still the mean SRT measurement of the same condition in noise, as shown above. Consequently, a bias
 444 may occur in the predictions presented here.

445 MisBEC-M and UD₁₀₀ exhibit the same behavior as for the measurements in noise, i.e., increasing SRTs with
 446 increasing distance between target speech source and receiver. In contrast, BSIM shows a slightly opposing trend.
 447 This indicates that MisBEC-M and UD₁₀₀ are able to predict the detrimental effect of reverberation on intelligibility

Figure 8. The middle panel shows SRTs in quiet predicted by the MisBEC-M model for two speech azimuths (circles: 0° , triangles: 90°) at four distinct receiver positions. The diotic condition without reverberation is denoted by the diamond symbol. Error bars represent the interindividual standard error. For comparative purposes, the mean measured SRTs (left panel) and predicted SRTs using the UD₁₀₀ model (right panel) and the original BSIM (represented by gray lines) are replotted from Fig. 5 in [14].

448 in quiet, which is not the case for the original BSIM. Interestingly, all models predict slightly higher SRTs for speech
 449 from the side compared to speech from the front at receiver positions 1-3, which is not observed in the measurements.
 450 This effect is strongest for MisBEC-M. The higher SRT values at receiver position 4 for speech from 0° compared
 451 to 90° can be attributed to the fact that the source for speech from 0° was further away from the listener than the
 452 source from 90° due to geometrical limitations of the simulated room (see Figure 1 in [14]). This effect is consistently
 453 predicted by all three models. MisBEC-M shows a bias toward lower SRTs for all predicted conditions in quiet, which
 454 is a consequence of the calibration of the model to the noise condition. Our study design accepted this bias, as we
 455 wanted a fixed model setting for all conditions. The larger standard errors (error bars) in the measurements as well
 456 as in the predictions of all three models for SRTs in quiet suggest that individual pure-tone audiograms, even for
 457 individuals with normal hearing, should not be neglected when predicting SRTs in quiet conditions.

458 Figure 9 presents a correlation analysis in the same format as Figure 7. Symbols represent speech azimuth: circles for
 459 0° , triangles for 90° , and diamonds for diotic speech without reverberation. A comparison of the predictive accuracy of
 460 the MisBEC-M and UD₁₀₀ models reveals a mixed picture: MisBEC-M exhibits a higher correlation (R^2) for individual
 461 data, whereas UD₁₀₀ achieves a higher correlation for the group mean and exhibits no bias. The MisBEC-M model
 462 underestimates SRTs by about 2 dB on average. Both models clearly outperform the original BSIM for this dataset.

Figure 9. The middle panel shows predicted SRTs in quiet using the MisBEC-M model compared to measured SRTs at different speech azimuths (circles: 0°, triangles: 90°) and the diotic condition without reverberation (diamonds), following the format of Figure 6. The left and right panels are replotted from Fig. 6 in [14] for comparison and show experimental data and predictions of the original BSIM and the UD₁₀₀ model, respectively.

Figure 10. Displays Δ SRTs of the German matrix sentence test, where speech and noise are presented at mirrored angles (x° and $-x^\circ$, with x ranging from -90° to 90°). The measured reference data (gray, replotted from [32]) are averaged across both sides, resulting in symmetrical mean values and a normative area (mean \pm 1 standard deviation). Predictions from the blind model MisBEC-M (squares) and the reference model BSIM (2010) (crosses, replotted from [32]) are compared to the measured data.

463 3.3. Dataset III – SRT benefits for symmetrical directions of arrival of speech and noise

464 Figure 10 shows the binaural gain (Δ SRTs) as measured in dataset III [32], i.e., the benefit in SRTs relative
 465 to the co-located (S_0N_0) configuration. In this respect, this display differs from Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.4, where
 466 absolute SRTs values were shown. This evaluation approach results in a narrower normative area (mean \pm 1 standard
 467 deviation) compared to the absolute thresholds used by [10] and [14]. In the context of comparing model predictions
 468 with measurements, this represents a more stringent criterion for prediction accuracy. The measured data and BSIM

Figure 11. Experimental data and predictions of the MisBEC-M model for dataset IV. Psychometric functions were fitted to all data points from SRT 20/80 measurements for $S_0 N_0$ (dashed line) and $S_\pi N_0$ (solid line). Horizontal error bars represent the mean and standard deviation of measured SRT 20/80 values (black) and interpolated SRT 50 values (gray). The prediction of MisBEC-M for $S_0 N_0$ is marked with an asterisk, and the prediction for $S_\pi N_0$ with a cross.

469 predictions were taken from [32] for comparison. In general, both the original BSIM as well as the MisBEC-M model
 470 predict SRT benefits which increase with increasing azimuthal separation and then flatten out for wide angular source
 471 separations.

472 MisBEC-M predictions exhibit a somewhat asymmetric erratic course in that the SRT benefit is generally well
 473 predicted for speech from one side, but slightly underestimated for speech from the other side. BSIM also shows an
 474 underestimated SRT benefit, but in a more symmetrical manner. This suggests a slight scattered uncertainty in the
 475 predicted SRT values of MisBEC-M. For large azimuth separations greater than $\pm 60^\circ$, predictions of MisBEC-M are
 476 slightly closer to the experimental data than predictions of BSIM. A statistical comparison of the predictions reveals
 477 a slightly higher R^2 for BSIM compared to MisBEC-M model (0.94 vs. 0.88). However, all other performance metrics
 478 listed in Table 2 are worse for BSIM: Bias (1.3 dB vs. 0.0 dB), mean absolute error (MAE) (1.4 dB vs. 0.9 dB), root
 479 mean square error (RMSE) (1.7 dB vs. 1.1 dB), and maximum absolute error (MaxAE) (3.6 dB vs. 2.5 dB). Note that the
 480 measured reference data were averaged across both sides and spline-interpolated for this analysis due to the different
 481 azimuth sampling. If the model predictions are also averaged across both sides, the R^2 values are nearly identical for
 482 both models, and the differences in all other performance metrics increase in favor of the MisBEC-M model.

483 3.4. Dataset IV – binaural unmasking of phase-inverted speech in diotic noise

484 Black symbols in Figure 11 show the data measured in this study for diotic speech and noise ($S_0 N_0$) and speech with
 485 inverted phase at one ear and diotic noise ($S_\pi N_0$), i.e., the adaptively tracked SNRs of 20% and 80% correctly recognized

486 words. Error bars represent ± 1 standard deviation. SRTs (gray) were derived from these data by interpolation (see
487 above). Psychometric functions were fitted to the data from all subjects and are shown as dashed and solid lines,
488 respectively. As expected, there was a considerable SRT benefit of about 10 dB due to phase inversion of the speech
489 signal in diotic noise. This benefit is very well predicted by MisBEC-M (model predictions as indicated by the asterisk).

490 4. General Discussion

491 4.1. General model performance and possible applications

492 The evaluations of the present study indicate that the inaccuracies of human binaural processing with respect to
493 interaural gain and delay in the equalization stage of an EC-based model can be implemented by a representative mis-
494 tuning. This allows replacing the previously employed Monte Carlo simulations by a much more efficient deterministic
495 computation. This front end, when combined with the MTD-based blind back end in the proposed MisBEC-M model,
496 is a fully blind prediction model which performed on par with the non-blind reference models for the datasets tested
497 here. The model was able to predict all relevant main effects of the datasets. This included the binaural benefit in
498 anechoic conditions and the interaction of binaural benefit and room reverberation (dataset I). The capability of the
499 model to predict these effects can be attributed to the binaural front end, and good predictions were achieved with
500 both types of back ends (SII-based and MTD-based). However, to achieve this, some fine tuning of the SII was required.
501 This indicates that front end and the back end in this model architecture do not act completely independently, in
502 other words, that the front end's processing produces an output, which may be rated differently by different speech
503 intelligibility back ends.

504 The MisBEC-M model also predicts the detrimental effect of reverberation on the (far-field) target speech
505 (dataset II), which becomes obvious in conditions without binaural benefit (S_0N_0). This can be attributed to the
506 back end, which apparently is disturbed by reverberation of the target speech in a similar manner as human listeners.
507 Furthermore, there is a reduction of binaural benefit for far-field sound sources, which is also predicted correctly.
508 This can be attributed mainly to the front end processing and a proper analysis of its output by the back end. The
509 effect of azimuthal separation of speech and noise for non-frontal speech (dataset III) as well as the benefit of pure
510 binaural unmasking due to phase inversion (dataset IV) are also well captured by the model front end. The inclusion
511 of threshold-simulating noise also allowed the model to predict SRTs in quiet (dataset II), although a small prediction
512 bias remained. Taken together, the proposed model is a versatile prediction model which – in contrast to the reference
513 models – only requires the binaural ear signals consisting of a (possibly reverberant) speech and noise mix. In principle,
514 this makes the model capable of continuous SI monitoring, e.g., in hearing devices in which the processing strategies

515 could be optimized based on the model output and/or adapted to changing acoustic environments. However, more
516 evaluations are needed to evaluate the potential of the model for such applications.

517 4.2. Variability observed for the MTD back end

518 Since the binaural front end produces a binaurally enhanced time signal, it can in principle be combined with
519 any signal-based back end. While the MTD back end employed in this study produced accurate predictions, some
520 aspects are worth noting for future considerations. In particular, we found that the reference MTD values used to
521 predict SRTs at 50% SI are close to the lower saturation limit of the mapping function (see Figure 3). This has two
522 key implications. First, the small variability in MTD values introduces relevant uncertainty in the predicted SRTs.
523 Smoothing interpolation, as described in Section 2.5.2, helps mitigate this uncertainty by providing a more stable
524 and continuous relationship between MTD and SNR. We expect that averaging across several seconds stabilizes the
525 prediction properly and is still suited for online monitoring of SI in practical applications like controlling speech
526 enhancement algorithms in hearing instruments. Second, the availability of substantial headroom at higher and ceiling
527 SI levels enables a detailed analysis of speech degradation under more favorable conditions, offering the opportunity to
528 extend the model’s predictive capability to subjective listening effort (LE) as demonstrated by [4] using a comparable
529 modeling framework.

530 The MTD back end is also more sensitive to the speech signal used as input than models using, e.g., speech-shaped
531 noise tokens representing the input signals. This is done, for instance, in the original EC/SII model [10] and BSIM [1].
532 This means that slightly different MTD values will result when using, e.g., different sentences from the same speech
533 test. For the datasets tested in this study, this did not appear to cause larger model inaccuracies, but it is possible
534 that the resulting variability will make predictions less accurate in other datasets and especially when the model is
535 applied to free running speech.

536 4.3. Limitations and alternative model approaches

537 One obvious limitation of the proposed blind model is its limitation to stationary noise or, more specifically, to
538 noise which does not contain speech-like modulations. This is due to the modulation-based selection in the front
539 end between EC_{\min} and EC_{\max} processing and for the selection of the better ear. Furthermore, speech-like maskers
540 containing phones cannot be distinguished from target phones in the back end, likely causing it to confuse target and
541 masker components and, hence, to produce inaccurate SI predictions.

542 This study is further limited in the range of datasets used for evaluation. The present datasets were chosen to test
 543 specific components of the model approaching realistic scenarios, but future work should include a larger variety of
 544 listening conditions. Furthermore, block processing, which is essential for continuous monitoring applications, has not
 545 been used in this evaluation and could impair the estimation of ILD and ITD and therefore reduce the importance or
 546 optimal amount of artificial inaccuracies.

547 In principle, the model is also able to predict the influence of hearing loss by accounting for absolute hearing
 548 thresholds, but the prediction accuracy for hearing-impaired listeners in binaural listening conditions remains to be
 549 tested.

550 An interesting conceptual comparison could be made between the proposed model, which considers the binaural
 551 unmasking based on EC processing in the binaural front end, and models incorporating binaural processing at a higher
 552 level of information. For example, the recent, more extensively trained “PHOBI” model [36], uses two monophonic
 553 posteriorgrams and a better-ear glimpsing-inspired binaural integration, and shows comparable accuracy in predicting
 554 dataset I. This corresponds to a binaural feature integration in higher stages of the human nervous system, i.e., at a
 555 level where phone posterior probabilities can be processed. At such a high stage, the information used for binaural
 556 processing is very different from the waveform-based EC-processing employed in the proposed model, which can be
 557 assumed to take place on brain stem level in the human auditory pathway, as only at this low level the temporal
 558 resolution of the signal representation is precise enough for allowing signal subtraction (EC_{\min}). It is likely that the
 559 binaural processing approach of the PHOBI model will not predict binaural unmasking in the artificial condition with
 560 phase-inverted speech (dataset IV) because there is no “worse” ear with more information about the noise that could
 561 enhance the posteriorgram on the opposite side.

562 5. Conclusions

563 Based on the findings of this study the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 564 • The consequence of human binaural processing inaccuracies for speech intelligibility in noise can be modeled
 565 deterministically using a representative mistuning of the interaural gain and delay in the equalization stage of the
 566 EC model.
- 567 • This extremely simplifies the model compared to Monte Carlo Simulations.
- 568 • The MTD back end can predict the influence of reverberation on target speech.
- 569 • Prediction accuracy of this completely blind model reaches that of the intrusive reference models for the datasets
 570 tested here.

571 **6. Appendix: Detailed derivation of mistuning**

572 The expectation value of the absolute value of a normally distributed random variable with a mean of 0, i.e., $E[|X|]$
 573 for $X \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, is sought. The expectation value of a function $g(x)$ for a continuous random variable with density
 574 $f_X(x)$ is given as

$$\mathbb{E}[g(X)] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) f_X(x) dx. \quad (2)$$

575 In our case $g(x) = |x|$ and the density of the normal distribution is given as

$$f_X(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right).$$

576 Inserting these terms into Equation (2) and setting $\mu = 0$ gives

$$\mathbb{E}[|X|] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x| \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) dx.$$

577 Exploiting the symmetry of the density function and the absolute value gives

$$\mathbb{E}[|X|] = 2 \int_0^{\infty} x \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) dx.$$

578 Using the substitution $u = \frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}$ and thus $du = \frac{x}{\sigma^2} dx$, where for $x = 0 \Rightarrow u = 0$ and for $x \rightarrow \infty \Rightarrow u \rightarrow \infty$, we
 579 finally obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[|X|] &= 2 \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \int_0^{\infty} x \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) dx \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \int_0^{\infty} \sigma^2 e^{-u} du \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi} \cdot \sigma} \cdot \sigma^2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-u} du \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sigma \int_0^{\infty} e^{-u} du \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sigma \cdot [-e^{-u}]_0^{\infty} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sigma \cdot (0 - (-1)) \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sigma = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sigma \approx 0.7979 \cdot \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

580 6.1. Mistuning of level equalization – detailed derivation

581 Given two independent normal distributed random variables $X, Y \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, we search for the expected value of

$$E \left[\left| 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\left(\sqrt{10^{(\sigma X/20)} \cdot 10^{(\sigma Y/20)}} \right)^2 \right) \right| \right].$$

582 We simplify the expression under the square root to

$$(10^{(\sigma X/20)}) \cdot (10^{(\sigma Y/20)}) = 10^{\frac{\sigma(X+Y)}{20}}.$$

583 As this term is always positive, $(\sqrt{\dots})^2$ has no effect, and thus we can omit it and consider the logarithm

$$20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(10^{\frac{\sigma(X+Y)}{20}} \right) = 20 \cdot \frac{\sigma(X+Y)}{20} = \sigma(X+Y).$$

584 Considering the absolute value and exploiting $\sigma > 0$, we get

$$|\sigma(X+Y)| = \sigma \cdot |X+Y|.$$

585 Finally, we calculate the expected value to

$$E[\sigma \cdot |X+Y|] = E[|X+Y|] \cdot \sigma.$$

586 This expression is used in Section 2.4.1.

587 6.2. Alternative statistic approach for deriving the magnitude of the mistuning

588 An alternative approach to determining the necessary size of the mistuning, instead of utilizing the mean absolute
 589 deviation, would be to use the resulting standard deviation between the channels which is equivalent to the root mean
 590 square (RMS) of the differences obtained with the Monte Carlo method.

591 As stated in Section 2.4.1, the variance σ_Z^2 of the sum of two independent random variables with the same variance
 592 σ^2 is $2\sigma^2$, and thus $\sigma_Z = \sqrt{2} \cdot \sigma \approx 1.4142 \cdot \sigma$. In comparison to the mistuning calculated in Section 2.4.1 (in total
 593 between the channels), the mistuning to be introduced when using the standard deviation as a measure of the average
 594 effect would be approximately 25% larger, by a factor of $\sqrt{2}/\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 1.2533$.

595 Since the first approach yielded convincing results in preliminary experiments and showed no obvious tendency to
596 overestimate the binaural gain, this alternative larger mistuning was discarded.

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606 **Conflicts of interest**

607 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

608 **Data availability statement**

609 The experimental data of datasets I, II, and IV will be made available on request.

610 **Ethical approval**

611 The methods were approved by the ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg (protocol Drs.EK/2021/093).

612 **Glossary**

613 **ASR** automatic speech recognition

614 **BE** better ear

615 **BEL** better-ear listening

616 **BU** binaural unmasking
 617 **DNN** deep neural network
 618 **EC** equalization-and-cancellation
 619 **ILD** interaural level differences
 620 **ITD** interaural time differences
 621 **LE** listening effort
 622 **MAE** mean absolute error
 623 **MaxAE** maximum absolute error
 624 **MCS** Monte Carlo simulation
 625 **MTD** Mean Temporal Distance
 626 **RC** reference condition
 627 **RIR** room impulse responses
 628 **RMS** root mean square
 629 **RMSE** root mean square error
 630 **SI** speech intelligibility
 631 **SII** Speech Intelligibility Index
 632 **SNR** signal-to-noise ratio
 633 **SRT** speech reception threshold

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